

Indian women's participation, problems and remedies in Corporate Sector in India

Dr. Devaki Nilesh Rathod

Assistant Prof.in Economics

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Mahavidyalaya, Aundh, Pune-67

Corresponding Author- Dr. Devaki Nilesh Rathod

Email: -nileshrathodd@gmail.com

Abstract:-

Gender inequality which is sometimes called sex discrimination means receiving unequal treatment based solely on gender. Women are most commonly the subject of gender inequality in the workforce. The contribution of women in corporate sector is essential for the success and prosperity of nations across the world. While gender barriers have softened to a large extent at the workplace, India still has a fair bit of ground to cover when it comes to ensuring a supportive environment for women at work. For all the talk around gender equality, most women in corporate India, even today, have to battle biases and stereotypes at the workplace, and often do not get the same opportunities, work profile and remuneration as their male counterparts, even when they are fully deserving. While the overall representation of women in the private sector has most definitely gone up in recent times, the number of women in leadership positions is far from satisfactory. On their part, corporate will tell you how it is often an uphill task to recruit women candidates, even with the best of intent, due to a minuscule pool to choose from. On the other hand, these are several cases where women recruited struggle to stay on and prolong their stint, in the absence of a supportive environment.

In India, the participation of women in the workforce is a paltry 26% (2018), which is lower than what we have in Sri Lanka and Bangladesh. As per the Prime database, in 2019, out of 1,814 chief executives and MDs of NSE-listed companies in India, only 67, or 3.69% are women. This shows that the percentage of women CEOs/MDs, 40, or 3.2%, were women. According to the latest Monster Salary Index survey, women in India earn 19% less than men, reflecting the high gender pay gap in our country. At 17% of GDP, the economic contribution of Indian women is less than half the global average and compares unfavorably to 40% in China. Even in an advanced economy like the U.S., women constitute only around 45% of the workforce. All these data points clearly show that we are a long way from achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 5 pertaining to gender equality. An IMF report says that India's GDP would increase by 27% if women participation equaled that of men and as per a study by McKinsey, just a 10% increase in women participation in the labor force could add \$700 billion to India's GDP by 2025, which is a testament to the untapped reservoir of talent women could unleash upon the workforce.

Key words:- Gender, inequality, Women, Corporate Sector

Introduction:-

A major obstacle that comes in the way of women rising up the corporate ladder is when they return to work post starting a family. The government can create an enabling environment for women, by extending POSH & maternity Benefit Act to the informal sector, and facilitate in measures like flexible leave/work hours, enhanced childcare support and the other steps incentivize shared care giving between both parents. Women can also help their own cause by upskilling or resetting their skills while they are on long breaks or sabbaticals. The government also should also consider mandating equal pay for equal work and offering incentives like tax benefits or preferential business to those employers having women employees above a certain threshold. It must also encourage more women to take up science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) subjects, which would help expand the pool of available female talent in STEM-focused jobs, where currently women are thoroughly underrepresented. This can be achieved through a well-conceived awareness campaign targeted at school-going girls and their parents coupled with

mentoring from teachers to alter socio-cultural perceptions.

Objective of the Study:

- 1) To Study the trend of women participation in corporate sector in India
- 2) To study of inequalities in India in different areas.
- 3) To study problem and remedies of Indian Women's participation in corporate sector

Methodology:-

This present research paper is based on secondary data. This data has been collected from different annual reports and other websites.

Sector Trends of Women Participation in Corporate:-

Women make 70% of the purchasing decisions at home., women entrepreneurs get only 1% of the global procurement business. They are missing in the supply chain. They need to understand the need of the market better (Elizabeth Vazquez, CEO of We Connect International) In 2021, an international consulting and management firm called Booz and Company released "The Third Billion, a global ranking of the level of economic

empowerment attained by women on 128 countries. The Indicators used included equal pay for equal work, non-discrimination policies, the male-to-female employee ratio, and equality in terms of female managers and Senior business leaders. India rated quite poorly at spot 115. Further, the International Labor Force recently reported that the rate of female participation in the total labor force in India had fallen from 37% in 2004-05 to 29% in 2009-10, leaving India at the lowest spot out of 131 countries.

Gathering of quantitative and qualitative data from the six largest publicly-traded Indian Software

companies, provide insight into state of female employment in one of the most important and rapidly growing economic sectors in the country. Using NASSCOM's annual industry rating from 2007-2012 the study has put together a list of the six software companies headquartered in India that appeared in the top five spots at least twice between the years 2007-2012. These.. These companies are Tata Consultancy Services Ltd. Infosys Ltd., Wipro, Wipro Ltd., HCL Tech. LTD., Tech Mahindra and Mahindra Satyam.

Table No.1: Representation of Women in Indian IT Industry

Sr.No.	Name of IT Industry	Number of Women on Board	Number of Women Holding Executive Management Position
1.	Tata Consultancy Services Ltd.	1/14	2/30
2	Wipro Ltd.	0/12	2/23
3	Infosys Ltd.	1/15	1/14
4	HCL Tech.Ltd.	1/19	0/18
5	Tech.Mahindra	0/11	1/7
6	Mahindra Satyam	1/16	0/6

Source: NASSCOMs, Annual Report

Women's Participation in the organized workforce in India is lower than in other countries due to historic traditional and cultural reasons, says Subhash A. K. Rao, director of human resources at Cisco's India arm. The (the other countries) have had their women participate in the organized workforce earlier than us (Indians). It is a journey and we are only going up.

The percentage of women in junior management in the 11 multinational firms surveyed is at least 30, but drops to less than 10 at the senior level. In a study on four countries the Gender Diversity Benchmark for Asia was done, the proportion of women in multinationals across junior, middle and senior management levels was the lower in India. The proportion of women employees in Japan and Singapore is 33.8% and 43.8% respectively.

Table 2: Gender wise Estimates of Employment in India:-

Sr.No.	Employment Measures	Men	Women	Total
1	Workforce (in thousands)	3,36,592	1,29,678	4,66,270
2	Workforce Participation Rate (%)	81.1% Population aged over 15 Years	33.1% of Population aged over 15 Years	57.8% of population aged over 15 years
3	Employment in organized Sector (in thousand)	45,784	10,716	56,450
4	Gender Composition of organized Sector (%)	81%	19%	100%
5	IT Workforce in (in thousands)	1629	671	2300
6	Gender Composition of IT workforce (%)	70% of IT workers	30% of IT workers	100%

ILO EAPEP (Estimate and Projections for Economically active population for 2008

*National Informatics Centre, Ministry of Labor, Government of India, (2009), the above estimates are for the year 2006, published in 2009. Estimates for 2008 based on (NASSCOM, 2010a) and (NASSCOM, 2009) Women exist from corporate sector due to family pressure and child rearing which is one of the biggest problems, says Jessie Paul, chief marketing officer and member of the diversity council at Wipro Technologies Ltd. the global arm of India's third largest software firm by revenues. It is not so easy to come back after passing a long time at home. The other people (Whom you worked with) would have reached a

certain place. (poornima Mohandas, 2009) Motherhood is traditionally the fulcrum of an Indian women's identity her highest achievement (Kakar 1988). It confers on her a sense of respectability and authority, thus strengthening her conjugal home. Chaplin, (1985) stated that due to restructuring and retrenchment many multinational companies are offloading complex managerial tasks to secretarial staff. In spite of having their management degrees many secretarial and administrative staff find it difficult to join the management degrees many secretarial and administrative staff find it difficult to join management track due to their lack of cultural

capital. They remain in administrative jobs which are usually associated with short term contracts and after at risk of retrenchment. The above Table 2 states the proportion of adult women in paid employment in India is only about 33%. The unorganized sector itself accounts for over 90% of the total workforce according to the National Sample Survey 2004-05.

***Problem faced by working women in India:-**

1. Mental Harassment:- It is an age old convention that women are less capable and inefficient in working as compared to men. The attitude which considers women unfit for certain jobs holds back women. In spite of the constitutional provisions, gender bias obstacles in their recruitment. In addition to this, the same attitude governs injustice of unequal salaries for the same job. The true equality has not been achieved even after 75 years of independence. Working in such conditions inevitably puts strain on women to greater extent as compared to men, thus making them less eager in their career.

2. Sexual Harassment:- Today, almost all working women are prone to sexual harassment irrespective of their status, personal characteristics and the types of their employment. They face sexual harassment on way on transports, at working places, educational institutions and hospitals, at home and even in police stations when they go to file complaints. It is shocking that the law protectors are violating and outraging modesty of women. Most of them tend to be concentrated in the poor service jobs whereas men are in an immediate supervisory position, which gives them an opportunity to exploit their subordinate women.

3. Discrimination:- However, Indian women still face blatant discrimination at their workplace. They are often deprived of promotions and growth opportunities at work places but this doesn't apply to all working women. A majority of working women continue to be denied their right to equal pay under the Equal Remuneration Act, 1976 and are underpaid in comparison to their male colleagues. This is usually the case in factories and labor-oriented industries.

4. No Safety of Working Women While Traveling:- Typically, the orthodox mindset in the Indian Society makes it difficult for a working woman to balance her domestic environment with the professional life. In some families, it may not be acceptable to work after six o'clock. Those families that do accept these working hours may experience considerable anxiety every day about a woman's safety while traveling. So many issues affect a working woman because she is closely protected or watched by her family and the society.

5. Lack of Family Support:- Lack of proper family support is another issue that working women suffer from. At the times the family doesn't

support women to leave the household work and go to office. They also resist for women working till late in office which also hampers the performance of the women and this also affects their promotion.

6. Insufficient Maternity Leaves:- Insufficient maternity leave is another major issue that is faced by working mothers. This not only affects the performance of women employees at work, but is also detrimental to their personal lives.

7. Job insecurity:- Unrealistic expectations, especially in the time of corporate reorganizations, which sometimes puts unhealthy and unreasonable pressures on the employee, can be a tremendous source of stress and suffering. Increased workload, extremely long work hours and intense pressure to perform at peak levels all the time for the same pay, can actually leave an employee physically and emotionally drained. Excessive travel and too much time away from family also contribute to an employee's stressors.

8. Workplace Adjustments:- Adjusting to the workplace culture, whether in a new company or not, can be a communication pattern of the boss as well as the co-workers, can be a lesson of life. Maladjustment to workplace cultures may lead to subtle conflicts with colleagues or even with superiors. In many cases office politics or gossips can be major stress inducers.

9. Other reasons:- It includes personal demographics like age, level of education, marital status, number of children, personal income, and number of jobs currently held where you work for pay and work situation characteristics like job tenure, size of employing organizations, hours worked per week.

Conclusion:-

Corporate India too can take certain steps to eliminate gender biases and empower women in the workplace. While organizations, on the whole, are much more open to hiring women, they must remember that recruitment itself is just the beginning of a long journey. Companies must do more such that women employees prolong their careers and have equal growth opportunities as their male counterparts. Corporates must shed their biases and offer women recruits dynamic roles, help them acquire new skills and foster an inclusive work environment. Women empowerment at the workplace can be realized only when men act as true allies and extend their wholehearted support to this cause. The male leadership should be sensitized to promote diversity, help their women colleagues thrive and contribute equally to the organization's growth. Flexibility and sensitivity should be incorporated in the organization's policies for women employees to realize their fullest potential. Another positive step from India Inc. would be to institute more awards and recognitions—exclusively for women at work. These can have great aspiration

value and motivate young girls, women in middle management and woman leaders to continue in their professional journey and strive to secure leadership roles. Each such award winner also becomes a role model and inspiration for hundreds of other women professionals.

Organizations should set tangible goals for gender diversity at the workplace, and keep reassessing the targets until gender parity is achieved. Tokenism must give way to concrete actionable steps. The leadership must be completely aligned with the company's diversity agenda and the need for achieving gender parity at work. Anti-harassment policies should be strengthened while biases-be it in hiring or allocation of roles should be identified and eliminated. Specially curated workshops conducted by experts can be useful for capacity building in women employees. Companies can also invite woman leaders and achievers to interact with and inspire their staff by sharing their experience and learning .In house mentorship programs can help identify high potential women employees, who can then be groomed for senior management roles. Entrepreneurship is yet another avenue for boosting participation of women in the workforce and opening up a host of opportunities for them. The government can do its bit by providing easier access to finance to aspiring woman entrepreneurs through scheme such as MUDRA, Fostering women entrepreneurship will not only empower women by making them economically independent but also create several role models who will inspire other fellow women to start their own venture, setting in motion a virtuosos cycle. The government must also ensure robust ecosystem for skilling and grooming budding woman entrepreneurs. For India to develop in the truest sense, we cannot afford to have half our population, lagging behind in terms of workforce participation. A gender-equal workplace and more women across Board rooms will be a refinishing feature of the new, vibrant India that awaits us, Policymakers and business houses must play their due roles, complementing each other's efforts to expedite this journey. However, at the end of the day, women themselves will have to come forward and alter the narrative-they have to script their own stories. Women today should work hard to build supportive ecosystems for themselves-both at home and at work. They need to be forthright in engaging with peers and supervisors at work and spouse/family and confidently articulate their ambition to build a professional career. Women must themselves initiate the process for securing a meaningful professional opportunity and pursue it for as long as she desire. Now is a good time for this.

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